

A Formal Methodology for Sequential Propagation Inference in Bayesian Networks (SPI-BN): Applied to causation modeling in the field of AI

Eduardo Macias-Avila

CIDESI, Apodaca Nuevo León, México

 <https://orcid.org/https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6438-1119>, eduardo.macias@cidesi.edu.mx

Jesus M. Orona-Hinojos

DataSc CG, DFW, Texas, USA

 <https://orcid.org/https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6693-3581>, jesus.orona@datasc-consultant.com

Lizbeth A. Huerta-Larumbe

DataSc CG, Saltillo, Coahuila, México

 <https://orcid.org/https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9574-1535>,
lizbeth.huerta@datasc-consultant.com

A. Yamaguchi Torres-Valdez

DataSc CG, Saltillo, Coahuila, México

 <https://orcid.org/https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8607-1990>,
yamaguchi.torres@datasc-consultant.com

Abstract: This article demonstrates the development of a novel method that allows obtain the path of evidence propagation through the Bayesian network to be traced, named Sequential Propagation Inference in Bayesian Networks (SPI-BN). Unlike previous algorithms based on message passing between network nodes, where probability calculations for each node are obtained after receiving all messages, in this method, evidence is introduced directly at its corresponding node, and probability changes propagate through its neighboring nodes. From there, the update continues to propagate sequentially across the network. This approach allows for real-time probability updates as evidence arrives at each node. A mathematical proof is included showing that the results produced by this method are equivalent to those obtained by standard Bayesian evidence propagation methods. The new method, SPI-BN, is demonstrated using a reference Bayesian network applied to FMECA (Failure Mode and Effects Critical Analysis) as a case study. This enables tracking the evidence propagation path, and reduces global computational complexity by avoiding recalculation of all messages when new evidence arrives. The method can be parallelized and allows us to treat the Bayesian network in modular components. Since the method can process evidence sequentially, it becomes possible to prioritize and input evidence with the most significant network impact. The work presents a potential application of AI-Algorithms in diverse engineering domains.

Keywords: Conditional Probabilities, Evidence Propagation, Bayesian-Networks, Expert System, Causation Modeling, Artificial Intelligence Algorithms,

1 Introduction

A Bayesian network is a graphical model representing a set of random variables and their conditional dependencies through a directed acyclic graph. The network consists of nodes connected by directed edges. Nodes represent random variables, while directed edges represent conditional dependencies, connecting parent nodes with their respective child nodes. Each child node has an associated probability function that takes the specific values of parent nodes as input and returns the probability of the variable represented in the node. This network type can be used to determine the probability of a subset of variables based on the values of other variables, which are considered evidence. The mechanism for determining these probabilities is known as evidence propagation.

Different algorithms have been developed for evidence propagation in Bayesian networks, classified into exact and approximate methods [Castillo, 1998, Koller, 2009]. Exact methods leverage the structure of conditional probabilities for evidence propagation [Castillo, 1998, Koller, 2009, Pearl, 1988], one of the first being the evidence propagation algorithm for polytree-type Bayesian networks developed by Kim and Pearl [Kim, 1990, Pearl, 1986]. In these networks, each node divides the polytree into two disconnected polytrees: one containing nodes accessible through the node's parents, and another containing nodes accessible through routes passing through child nodes [Castillo, 1998, Pearl, 1988, Kim, 1990, Pearl, 1986]. The propagation process can be performed in such graphs by combining information from different subgraphs through message passing between subgraphs. The probability of each node is calculated once all messages from its parent and child nodes are received. Not all Bayesian networks are polytrees; some are multiply connected networks. Two of the most important propagation methods for such networks are conditioning and clustering methods [Castillo, 1998, Koller, 2009]. The fundamental idea of the conditioning propagation method is to cut multiple paths between nodes by assigning values to a reduced set of variables, as proposed by Pearl [Pearl, 1986] and [Suermondt, 1990]. On the other hand, the clustering propagation method groups a set of nodes into a single cluster, allowing the network to take a polytree-like structure.

Approximate propagation algorithms refer to those that calculate node conditional probabilities approximately. The basic idea is to generate a sample of size N using techniques such as probabilistic logic sampling, likelihood weighting, or Gibbs sampling, which rely on the structure and conditional dependencies of the network and use this sample to calculate approximate probabilities of certain events based on evidence [Castillo, 1998, Fung, 1990, Shachter, 1990, Pearl, 1987, Koller, 2009]. Approximate inference methods based on sampling are valuable when exact (deterministic) methods become computationally infeasible. This typically occurs in large or densely connected Bayesian networks, where exact inference requires operations over high-dimensional joint distributions or the construction of complex junction trees, both of which scale poorly with network size and connectivity. However, these approximate methods often trade off important properties such as explainability, traceability, and the ability to justify inferences. This trade-off can be problematic in domains like medical or legal expert systems, where user trust and transparency are critical. Additionally, many sampling-based approaches are not well-suited for real-time applications,

as incorporating new evidence may require restarting the sampling process or regenerating a large number of weighted samples, limiting their efficiency in dynamic environments.

Approximate inference methods based on variational principles have been extensively developed for Bayesian networks and other probabilistic graphical models [Koller, 2009, Winn, 2005, Blei, 2017]. These methods work by optimizing a lower bound (typically the Evidence Lower Bound, or ELBO) on the true log-likelihood of the data, approximating the posterior distribution with a simpler, tractable distribution drawn from a parameterized family. While variational inference is computationally efficient and scalable for large-scale models, standard (batch) variational methods are generally not well-suited for real-time or sequential evidence updates. Incorporating new observations typically requires re-optimizing the variational objective from scratch, which can be computationally expensive and impractical in time-sensitive applications [Tomasetti, 2022]. However, recent developments such as Updating Variational Bayes (UVB) [Tomasetti, 2022] address these limitations by allowing for incremental updates without full re-optimization.

Bayesian networks have been used to develop expert systems for predictive modeling of Machine Learning ML / AI and managing uncertainty in various decision-making processes. These networks use a probabilistic approach based on Bayes' Theorem, representing cause-and-effect relationships between variables through nodes and directed edges. Although these networks are powerful tools for modeling uncertainty, interpreting their results can be complex, especially in large or highly interconnected networks. This makes it difficult to explain how a specific conclusion is reached, which is problematic in applications where justifying the result is as important as the result itself (e.g., medical diagnosis or critical decision making). Lacave et al. [Lacave, 2002] review the methods of generating explanations in Bayesian networks, dividing explanations into evidence, model, and reasoning categories. Reasoning explanation methods seek to find the routes through which information flows in the Bayesian network. Wellman [Wellmann, 1990] proposed an explanation generation method based on a qualitative analysis of the reasoning chain, which involves transforming the causal Bayesian network into a probabilistic network, although its main problem is lack of precision due to the combination of negative and positive influences. S. Renooij and L. van der Gaag [Renooij, 1999] sought to alleviate this problem by classifying influences as strong and weak, although it remains a qualitative approach.

Unlike traditional inference approaches, the algorithm proposed in this work—Sequential Propagation Inference in Bayesian Networks (SPI-BN)—updates probabilities incrementally and locally as evidence arrives at each node, allowing the exact path of evidence propagation to be traced in real time. Furthermore, the method does not require reprocessing or reinserting previously observed evidence when new evidence is introduced. It also opens the possibility for modular decomposition of the network into independent subcomponents, each potentially capable of processing local evidence and synchronizing with the rest of the system. This could enable scalable, distributed inference while still preserving the ability to generate precise, traceable explanations.

2 Formulation method of the evidence propagation algorithm.

The paper is organized as follows: first, the evidence propagation method for a set of nodes is described separately, developed for a complete network in Section 2.0. Section 2.1 to 2.5 presents the different types of evidence propagation—namely backward, forward, lateral, and internal—within a unified framework for Bayesian single structures. This integrated presentation enhances the clarity and cohesion of the method. Moreover, Section 2.6 provides a mathematical explanation for the Proof of equivalence between the SPI-BN method and Exact Inference. The algorithms for new method is described in Section 2.7, which was named Sequential Propagation Inference in Bayesian Networks (SPI-BN). The Python implementation of the algorithm is available in the supplementary materials. The application and some cases of the proposed method to FMECA problems is presented in Section 3.0 Result. While, along subsections by cases with an analysis of the resulting Bayesian network outcomes. In Section 4.0 was discussion of advantage and the relevance of knowing the path of flow evidence inside the structure of Bayesian networks.

2.1 Bayesian Network Section Analysis

This section presents the formulation of the evidence propagation algorithm within the Bayesian network. In this case, it is necessary to account for the flow of evidence in different directions, including situations where the propagation occurs internally within a fused node. To this end, Figure 1 illustrates a Bayesian network.

Figure 1: Multiply Connected Bayesian Network.

This Bayesian network is multiply connected. To enable its use, two of the nodes can be merged to form a polytree network, as shown in Figure 2.

2.2 Marginal Propagation

Marginal propagation in Bayesian networks is performed when no evidence has been presented. In other words, in the absence of any observed data, the network

Figure 2: Bayesian Network with Merged Nodes.

computes the marginal probabilities solely based on its prior distributions and inherent structure. In this procedure, before starting evidence propagation, it is necessary to calculate the marginal probabilities of each node in the Bayesian network. This provides a baseline state of the network's probabilistic beliefs before any new evidence is incorporated. Using the Bayesian network shown in Figure 2, the marginal probability is calculated as the starting point. The

probability of the node A takes the value A_i is typically denoted by $P(A = A_i)$. However, since probability expression will appear frequently throughout the formulas in this work, we adopt a simplified notation. Specifically, we will write $a_i = P(A = A_i)$, using a lowercase letter to represent the probability of the corresponding event. In the case where joint probabilities of two variables are considered, such as for the merged node of variables B and C, these are calculated jointly as shown in equation 1.

$$(b_j c_k) = \sum_i P(B_j, C_k | A_i) \cdot a_i \quad (1)$$

The probabilities of the other nodes would be calculated in a similar manner. Unlike other evidence propagation methods, the proposed approach updates probabilities using the component of the marginal distributions that represent the baseline. For this method, parameters Φ referred to as probability factors would be used, these factors update with the addition of evidence in the Bayesian network. Their initial value is indeed the conditional probability. An example of a probability factor Φ^0 would be its initial value at the start of the algorithm, as in equation 2:

$$\Phi^0(B_j, C_k | A_i) = P(B_j, C_k | A_i) \quad (2)$$

From this point onward, depending on the node that serves as the evidence, the type of propagation within the network would be determined. Let's analyze each type of propagation within the network.

2.3 Backward Evidence Propagation

To explain the reasoning in Bayesian networks, it is necessary to observe how evidence propagates through the different nodes that compose the network. The

directed edges (arrows) indicate the flow of probabilistic influence, showing how each node's probability is updated based on the new evidence. This process typically starts at the evidence node and then updates the probabilities of its direct descendants and ancestors, continuing recursively until the entire network is covered. For this purpose, a portion of a Bayesian network is analyzed (in this case, a polytree is considered), as shown in Figure 3a.

Figure 3: Section of a Bayesian Network. (a) Nodes A and B in a Bayesian network with a parents neighbors and (b) Nodes B without a B_- follow node

The part to be analyzed corresponds to nodes A and B in a Bayesian network. In this part, A_+ refers to the nodes in the Bayesian network that precede node A , for which a probability $P(A_+)$ can be defined. Meanwhile, A_- refers to the set of nodes that follow node A but do not pass through node B . The set B_+ refers to the set of nodes that precede node B , excluding those connected through node A . The set of nodes B_- refers to the nodes that follow node B . To understand the combined effect between nodes A and B , we will calculate the probability of

$A = A_i$ and $B = B_j$, given that evidence is provided in the other nodes.

First, we will define the probability of $A=A_i$ without considering the effect of node B, meaning only the existing evidence in the sets of nodes A_+ and A_- . The probability of A, given this set of evidence (before receiving the evidence flow from node B and assuming we are in an iteration "n" where it is written as a superscript), would be expressed as equation 3:

$$a_i^n = P(A_i | A_+, A_-) \quad (3)$$

In this development, we will use a probability factor in place of the conditional probability. As we explain the method, it should become clear why we proceed in this manner. This probability factor will change as evidence flows into the corresponding nodes. However, it is important to clarify that initially, the probability factor is equal to the conditional probability at the beginning of the algorithm defined by equation 4.

$$\Phi^0(B_k | A_i, B_{+,j}) = P(B_k | A_i, B_{+,j}) \quad (4)$$

The probability of node $B = B_k$, due only to the evidence from the sets of nodes A_+ , A_- , and B_+ , is expressed as eq. 5:

$$b_k^n = \sum_{i,j} \Phi^0(B_k | A_i, B_{+,j}) a_i b_{+,j} \quad (5)$$

This equation 5, corresponds only to this portion of the Bayesian network, as shown in Figure 3b, not yet accounting for the effect of the nodes represented by B_- . Now, we will consider the other part of the evidence, corresponding to the nodes B_- as shown in the figure 3a. Assuming that $B = B_j$ occurs with a probability $b_j^n = P(B_j | A, B_+)$, then in a total of N_t events, the expected number of events where $B = B_j$, denoted as N_{Bj} , would be given by eq. 6:

$$N_{Bj} = b_j^n N_t \quad (6)$$

If we consider the effect of the set of nodes B_- on expected number of events where $B = B_j$, it would be necessary to discard a number of results where $B = B_j$, or conversely, eliminate results where $B \neq B_j$, depending on the type of effect that the evidence from B_- has on node B, so that the probability of $B = B_j$ can be updated to a new value. To achieve this, it is necessary to multiply by a factor s_j . Therefore, the new number of accepted results where $B = B_j$ is updated by eq. 7

$$N_{Bj} = b_j^n N_t s_j \quad (7)$$

From here, the probability of $B = B_j$, now considering the effect of the evidence contained in the sets of nodes A_+ , A_- , B_+ , and B_- , is expressed as eq. 8:

$$b_j^{n+1} = \frac{b_j^n N_t s_j}{\sum_j b_j^n N_t s_j} \quad (8)$$

It is possible to isolate s_j , such that the result is eq. 9:

$$\frac{b_j^{n+1}}{b_j^n} = \frac{s_j}{\sum_j b_j^n N_t s_j} = \frac{s_j}{N} \quad (9)$$

To obtain the probability that $A = A_i$, considering the effect of the evidence contained in the sets of nodes A_+ , A_- , B_+ , and B_- , the probability factor is used, which leads to the expression shown in equation 10:

$$\Phi^n(B_j | A_i) = \sum_k \Phi^n(B_j | A_i, B_{+,k}) b_{+,k} \quad (10)$$

Based on this equation, the probability of $A = A_i$ is obtained. by eq. 11:

$$a_i^{n+1} = \sum_j \Phi^n(B_j | A_i) a_i^n \frac{s_j}{N} = a_i^n \sum_j \Phi^n(B_j | A_i) \frac{b_j^{n+1}}{b_j^n} \quad (11)$$

The joint probability of $A = A_i$ and $B = B_j$, considering the effect of the evidence contained in the sets of nodes A_+ , A_- , B_+ , and B_- , can be calculated as eq. 12:

$$(a_i b_j)^{n+1} = a_i^n \Phi^n(B_j | A_i) \frac{b_j^{n+1}}{b_j^n} \quad (12)$$

It is important to clarify that the probability factor can be adjusted as iterations progress than shown in eq. 13.

$$\Phi^{n+1}(B_j | A_i, B_{+,k}) = \Phi^n(B_j | A_i, B_{+,k}) \frac{b_j^{n+1}}{b_j^n} \frac{a_i^n}{a_i^{n+1}} \frac{b_{+,k}^n}{b_{+,k}^{n+1}} \quad (13)$$

From here, finally it is demonstrate that eq. 14 :

$$b_j^{n+1} = \sum_{i,k} \Phi^{n+1}(B_j | A_i, B_{+,k}) b_{+,k}^{n+1} a_i^{n+1} \quad (14)$$

The equation 11 provides the probability change of node A based on the evidence received through node B.

2.4 Forward and Lateral Evidence Propagation

Regarding forward evidence propagation, it can be calculated as follows. For example, in Figure 3a, if node A receives an update of the evidence, then the flow of evidence to node B would be calculated as show in eq. 15:

$$b_j^{n+1} = \sum_{i,k} \Phi^n(B_j | A_i, B_{+,k}) b_{+,k}^n a_i^{n+1} \quad (15)$$

By applying a similar approach to the one used for forward propagation, the lateral evidence propagation from node A to node B_+ can be obtained. The

evidence propagation would be calculated as eq. 16:

$$b_{+,k}^{n+1} = b_{+,k}^n \sum_{i,j} \Phi^n(B_j | A_i, B_{+,k}) a_i^{n+1} \quad (16)$$

It is important to note that, whenever evidence passes through the nodes, the probability factor must be updated so that they are ready in case a new flow of evidence arrives, as shown in eq. 17.

$$\Phi^{n+1}(B_j | A_i, B_{+,k}) = \Phi^n(B_j | A_i, B_{+,k}) \frac{b_{+,k}^n}{b_{+,k}^{n+1}} \quad (17)$$

2.5 Internal Evidence Propagation within Merged Node.

In this case, assuming that one of the internal nodes turns out to be evidence, the changes in the merged node are calculated first. Looking at Figure 2, originally, the probability of node B within this merged node would be given by:

$$b_i^n = \sum_j (b_i c_j)^n \quad (18)$$

If new evidence is received at node B, the number N_t is adjusted to account for the new probability as show eq. 19.

$$N_t = \sum_{i,j} (b_i c_j)^n s_i \quad (19)$$

Which gives us:

$$b_i^{n+1} = \frac{\sum_j (b_i c_j)^n s_i}{N_t} = b_i^n \frac{s_i}{N_t} \quad (20)$$

Then, the probability of $C = C_j$ would be calculated as eq.21:

$$c_j^{n+1} = \frac{\sum_i (b_i c_j)^n s_i}{N_t} = \sum_i (b_i c_j)^n \frac{b_i^{n+1}}{b_i^n} \quad (21)$$

The combined probability within the merged node is given by eq. 22:

$$(b_i c_j)^{n+1} = (b_i c_j)^n \frac{b_i^{n+1}}{b_i^n} \quad (22)$$

2.6 Proof of equivalence between the SPI-BN method and Exact Inference Techniques

To demonstrate the correctness of the proposed evidence propagation method in Bayesian networks, we begin with a simple illustrative example, using a basic Bayesian network as shown in Figure 4. The method can be generalized to any polytree-structured Bayesian network by exploiting the fact that such networks can be partitioned into smaller substructures by introducing structural

Figure 4: Bayesian Network used in this example

cuts. These cuts isolate subgraphs such that inference can be performed locally within each subgraph, and then recombined according to the standard rules of belief propagation. Since the method yields Bayes-consistent results within each partition, and the combination of subresults respects the dependencies encoded in the original network, the overall inference remains equivalent to that obtained via traditional Bayesian reasoning. According to Bayes' rule, the posterior probability of an event A given some evidence (Ev) is computed as

$$P(A | Ev) = \frac{P(Ev, A)}{P(Ev)} \quad (23)$$

We now proceed to demonstrate how the proposed method yields the same expressions, in order to establish the equivalence between the standard Bayesian inference approach and our method. Prior to the application of the method, the probabilities of each node are given as marginal probabilities, meaning they are computed without conditioning on any evidence from other nodes. At this initial stage, the probability factors correspond directly to the conditional probabilities defined by the Bayesian network structure. for example:

$$\Phi^0(B_j | A_{1,i}) = P(B_j | A_{1,i}) \quad (24)$$

We begin by setting node C_1 as an evidence node, with the observed value $C_1 = 1$ (considering binary-valued nodes). According to the Bayesian network structure, evidence must be propagated backward toward node B. Following the procedure, the expression for node B is initially given by eq. 25:

$$b_j^{n+1} = \sum_k \Phi^n(C_{1,k} | B_j) b_j^n \frac{c_{1,k}^{n+1}}{c_{1,k}^n} \quad (25)$$

Incorporating the evidence $C_1 = 1$ when $n=0$, this expression simplifies to eq.26:

$$b_j^1 = \frac{P(C_{1,k} | B_j) b_j^0}{c_{1,k}^0} = \frac{P(C_{1,k} | B_j) b_j^0}{\sum_j P(C_{1,k} | B_j) b_j^0} \quad (26)$$

Furthermore, starting from node B, evidence propagation can be carried backward to nodes A_1 to A_n . We only present the propagation to node A_1 , as the corresponding expression for others nodes A can be easily derived eq. 27.

$$a_{1,i}^1 = \sum_{j,rest} \Phi^0(B_j | A_{1,i}, A_2, \dots, A_n) a_{1,i}^0 \prod_{k=2}^n a_k^0 \frac{b_j^1}{b_j^0} \quad (27)$$

Substituting terms into equation 27, we obtain that:

$$a_{1,i}^1 = \frac{\sum_{j,rest} P(C_{1,k} | B_j) P(B_j | A_{1,i}, A_2, \dots, A_n) a_{1,i}^0 \prod_{k=2}^n a_k^0}{\sum_j P(C_{1,k} | B_j) b_j^0} \quad (28)$$

Furthermore, starting from node B, evidence propagation can be carried forward to nodes C_2 to C_m , for example for node C_2 , we have:

$$c_{2,k}^1 = \sum_j \Phi^0(C_{2,k} | B_j) b_j^1 = \sum_j P(C_{2,k} | B_j) b_j^1 \quad (29)$$

The formulas that provide the probabilities of nodes C and A are identical to those obtained using Bayes' rule.

In our procedure, since backward propagation was performed, the probability factors have changed; they are no longer equivalent to the initial conditional probabilities, but are now given by:

$$\Phi^{n+1}(B_j | A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n) = \Phi^n(B_j | A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n) \frac{b_j^{n+1}}{b_j^n} \frac{\prod_{k=1}^n a_k^n}{\prod_{k=1}^n a_k^{n+1}} \quad (30)$$

We obtain eq.31:

$$\Phi^1(B_j | A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n) = P(B_j | A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n) \frac{b_j^1}{b_j^0} \frac{\prod_{k=1}^n a_k^0}{\prod_{k=1}^n a_k^1} \quad (31)$$

Only the nodes whose probabilities changed due to backward propagation update their probability factors; those affected by forward propagation remain un-

changed.

We introduce evidence at node $A_1 = 1$, but this evidence is incorporated starting from the values obtained in the Bayesian network solution when $C_1 = 1$. By proceeding in this manner, we obtain the solution corresponding to the combined evidence $A_1 = 1$ and $C_1 = 1$. In this case, we perform forward evidence propagation from node A_1 toward node B.

$$b_j^2 = \sum_{rest} \Phi^1(B_j | A_{1,i}, A_2, \dots, A_n) a_{1,i}^2 \prod_{k=2}^n a_k^1 \quad (32)$$

By substituting the probability factor(ec. 31), the ratio $\frac{b_j^1}{b_j^0}$ (ec. 26), $a_{1,i}^2 = 1$ because it is evidence, into Equation 32, we obtain:

$$b_j^2 = \frac{\sum_{rest} P(B_j | A_{1,i}, A_2, \dots, A_n) P(C_{1,k} | B_j) a_{1,i}^0 \prod_{k=2}^n a_k^0}{a_{1,i}^1 c_{1,k}^0} \quad (33)$$

Remembering the equation 28, we have that eq.34:

$$b_j^2 = \frac{\sum_{rest} P(B_j | A_{1,i}, A_2, \dots, A_n) P(C_{1,k} | B_j) a_{1,i}^0 \prod_{k=2}^n a_k^0}{\sum_{j,rest} P(B_j | A_{1,i}, A_2, \dots, A_n) P(C_{1,k} | B_j) a_{1,i}^0 \prod_{k=2}^n a_k^0} \quad (34)$$

This equation is equivalent to $P(B_j | A_{1,i}, C_{1,k})$ obtained using Bayes' rule.

We proceed with lateral propagation from node A_1 to node A_2 , which yields the following equation:

$$a_{2,l}^2 = \sum_{j,rest} \Phi^1(B_j | A_{1,i}, A_{2,l}, \dots, A_n) a_{1,i}^2 a_{2,l}^1 \prod_{k=3}^n a_k^1 \quad (35)$$

By substituting the probability factor(ec. 31), the ratio $\frac{b_j^1}{b_j^0}$ (ec. 26), $a_{1,i}^2 = 1$ because it is evidence, and eq.28 into equation 35, we obtain:

$$a_{2,l}^2 = \frac{\sum_{j,rest} P(B_j | A_{1,i}, A_{2,l}, \dots, A_n) P(C_{1,k} | B_j) a_{1,i}^0 a_{2,l}^0 \prod_{k=3}^n a_k^0}{\sum_{j,rest,l} P(B_j | A_{1,i}, A_{2,l}, \dots, A_n) P(C_{1,k} | B_j) a_{1,i}^0 a_{2,l}^0 \prod_{k=3}^n a_k^0} \quad (36)$$

This equation is equivalent to $P(A_{2,l} | A_{1,i}, C_{1,k})$ obtained using Bayes' rule. In our procedure, since lateral propagation was performed, the probability factors have changed; now they are given by:

$$\Phi^{n+1}(B_j | A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n) = \Phi^n(B_j | A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n) \frac{\prod_{k=2}^n a_k^n}{\prod_{k=2}^n a_k^{n+1}} \quad (37)$$

Thus, the probability factor can be applied to update the probabilities of A_2 through A_n . Finally, there would be forward propagation from node B to node C_2 . However, since there has been no backward propagation in this case, the likelihood factor remains equal to the conditional probability, and therefore the

calculation is trivial.

2.7 Algorithm of Sequential Propagation Inference (SPI-BN)

The calculation procedure for this algorithm is as follows:

1. Calculate the marginal probabilities in the Bayesian network.
2. Initialize the conditional probability factors, which would be equal to the conditional probabilities.
3. Define the order in which the evidence enters the Bayesian network.
4. The evidence node enters the network, defining the trajectory that the probability updates will follow in the Bayesian network (evidence flow), considering whether there were previously calculated evidence nodes in prior steps.
5. Update the probabilities in the nodes corresponding to the trajectory, verifying the type of evidence flow.
 - Internal evidence propagation within a merged node.
 - Backward evidence propagation.
 - Forward and lateral evidence propagation.
 - Update the probability factors.

Note: It is important to check the value of the probability of node; if it is equal to zero can be applied to the formula as a divisor, but you can remember that in this case, the probability factor is also equal to zero, and it is not necessary to make another calculation for this factor.

6. Check if the number of evidence nodes has been completed. If not, return to step 4.

From here, the updated probabilities in the Bayesian network can be obtained. In the case of receiving updates in the number of evidence nodes, the process can start from step 3.

The code used in this article can be found in the GitHub repository <https://github.com/eduardomaciasavila70-again/new-bayesian-network-code>

3 Results

As a first case of study, we chose the FMECA (Failure Mode and Effects Critical Analysis) for process of thermoforming car floor covering, developed in the paper of Belu et al. (2013) [Brahim, 2019, Belu, 2013]. This FMECA is used in the automotive industry to improve quality and product reliability, search path solutions, and take corrective actions in order to eliminate the failure mode and the adverse effects.

3.1 Application A: Thermoforming Process of "Car Floor Covering"

The method was tested in one case study, corresponding to "Build a Bayesian Network from FMECA in the Production of Automotive Parts reported by Ben Brahim [Brahim, 2019]. Regarding a Bayesian network is presented as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Bayesian network used in the example given by Ben Brahim et al [Brahim, 2019]

This work presents the resolution of a Bayesian network using a new method for evidence propagation. The proposed method allows for the visualization of how evidence spreads through a multiply connected Bayesian network. The results are compared with those obtained using the standard message-passing method. The Bayesian network used is shown in Figure 5, including the nodes and arrows that represent the relationships between them.

The names of each variable and the probabilities assigned to these nodes are showed in the Table I. If a variable has no parent nodes, the probabilities correspond to marginal probabilities. If the variable has parent nodes, the probabilities correspond to conditional probabilities. For the development of the proposed new method, the first step is to convert the multiply connected network into a polytree-type network. To achieve this, some of the nodes are merged. Figure 6 illustrates the structure of the network after the nodes have been merged. In this case, for example, considering the acronyms in Table 1, instead of having separate nodes for MTI and FM, a single fused node MTI-FM is used, which includes the combined marginal probabilities of both original nodes. A fused node such as B-F-VIH-SU has member nodes B, F, VIH, and SU. Its parent nodes are now MTI-FM and UM, which ultimately include the parents of the individual nodes B, F, VIH, and SU. Through programming, it is possible to compute a joint conditional probability for the fused node B-F-VIH-SU based on the conditional probabilities of its member nodes. The analysis of the original

Table 1: Variables used in the bayesian network

Variable	Name	Father Nodes	Probability
<i>PM</i>	Placing Material		0.7
<i>MTI</i>	Mould temp. Inadequate		0.6
<i>FM</i>	Flaw Material		0.4
<i>MM</i>	Mold Material	PM	0.0579,0.8552
<i>UM</i>	Unclean Mould		0.25
<i>B</i>	Burns	MTI	0, 0.9
<i>F</i>	Folds	FM,MTI	0.0,0.40,0.4,0.85
<i>VIH</i>	Variation in Hue	FM,MTI	0.056,0.316,0.316,0.576
<i>SU</i>	Spots Unclean	MTI,UM	0.0070,0.2787,0.3330,0.9307
<i>MD</i>	Material Defect	F,B	0.3775,0.6006,0.6006,0.8237
<i>MP</i>	Material Problem	F,B,VIH	0.0101,0.2357,0.2357,0.4614 0.2357,0.4614,0.4614,0.6870
<i>FC</i>	Functionality Compromised	F	0, 0.85
<i>CC</i>	Customer Claim	VIH	0, 0.95
<i>CR</i>	Customer Refusal	MM,MD,SU	0.1122,0.6791,0.6791,0.9626 0.6791,0.9626,0.9626,0.9626
<i>ANC</i>	Aspect Nonconforming	MM,MP,SU	0.3022,0.5264,0.5264,0.7505 0.5264,0.7505,0.7505,0.9747

network led to the creation of a new node, SUad, to allow its fusion with nodes MD and MP, resulting in the fused node MD-MP-SUad. The variable SUad is identical to the variable SU; however, this transformation enabled us to simplify the structure of the Bayesian network.

Figure 6: Bayesian network used in the example with merged nodes

3.2 Marginal Propagation

We will now describe how evidence propagation is carried out in this method. In this approach, the evidence nodes to be progressively added to the network are MTI, CR, and PM, in that order. The first step in this method is to obtain the marginal probabilities, which are presented in Figure 7 along with their corresponding table. In this case, the arrows in the figure represent the direction in which probabilities are computed at each node.

Figure 7: Results of Marginal Propagation in the Bayesian network

3.3 Case I: Mould Temperature Inadequate MTI=1

In the following case, we will examine how the evidence propagates when $MTI = 1$ (Mould Temperature Inadequate), as illustrated in the Figure 8, the direction of evidence propagation is indicated by arrows.

The propagation flow begins with internal propagation in the fused node MTI-FM. Here, we have internal propagation, the variable FM does not change since, because initially it is an independent node from MTI. It is observed that an inadequate mold temperature has a significant effect on the fused node B-F-VIH-SU, particularly on the variable B (Burns), where a very high temperature causes plastic burning, showing the greatest impact. Effects are also seen on other variables such as SU (spots), VIH (variation in Hue), and F (folds), although their effects are smaller. The propagation toward this node was of the forward propagation type.

The UM node shows no change in its probability because, as the propagation started with probability factors equal to the conditional probabilities, lateral propagation of evidence does not cause any change on . In fact, in all cases where lateral propagation occurs, no change will be observed for this same reason.

Figure 8: Results of Evidence Propagation in the Bayesian network when $MTI=1$

From the fused node B-F-VIH-SU, there is forward propagation toward the nodes MD-MP-SUad, CC, and FC, whose probability values show appreciable changes. From the node MD-MP-SUad, forward propagation continues toward the node CR-ANC, whose probability values show a lighter change. The probability factors in this step remain unchanged, still equal to the conditional probabilities.

3.4 Case II: Customer Refusal $CR=1$

In the following case, we will examine how evidence propagates when $CR = 1$ (Customer Refusal). Recall that in this case, we start from the marginal probability, as shown in the Figure 9, the direction of evidence propagation is indicated by arrows. In this case II, the evidence propagation flow begins with internal propagation within the fused node “CR-ANC.” Although ANC is part of the fused node, in the original network it was somewhat independent of CR, so its probability does not change significantly. Next, backward propagation occurs toward the nodes MD-MP-SUad and MM, where probability changes are observed for the causes that led to customer refusal. These causes are MD (material defect), SU (spots), and MM (missing material). From the MM node, backward propagation continues to the PM (placing material) node, which increases its probability. From the MD-MP-SUad node, backward propagation proceeds to the B-F-VIH-SU node, where the probabilities increase for causes such as Burns, Folds, and Variation in Hue. From this B-F-VIH-SU node, backward propagation continues to the MTI-FM and UM nodes, which also increase their probabilities. Since no additional evidence beyond the customer refusal is provided, many possible causes remain, which explains why their probabilities do not change drastically. From the same B-F-VIH-SU node, forward propagation then occurs toward the CC and FC nodes, whose probabilities increase slightly.

Figure 9: Results of Evidence Propagation in the Bayesian network when $CR=1$

In this case, the probability factors change; they are no longer equal to the conditional probabilities because evidence propagation occurred backward. This is important for the next calculation if an additional evidence node is introduced.

3.5 Case III: Customer Refusal, $CR=1$; Mould Temperature Inadequate, $MTI=1$

In the previous case, there were many causes for the customer refusal. Now, let us consider the case where additional evidence is available indicating that the mould temperature was inadequate, corresponding to $MTI = 1$ and $CR = 1$. In this case, as shown in Figure 10. We start from the results of the run where $CR = 1$, and then add the new evidence $MTI = 1$. In all cases where backward propagation occurred, the probability coefficients of the Bayesian network must be updated. Alternatively, the process could start with $MTI = 1$ and then run with evidence $CR = 1$, and the results should be identical. The propagation flow begins with internal propagation within the fused node $MTI-FM$, where FM decreases very slightly. Next, forward propagation occurs toward the node $B-F-VIH-SU$, primarily affecting the variable B (Burns) and, to a lesser but still notable extent, the variables F , VIH , and SU . Unlike the previous case, since the probability coefficients are no longer equal to the initial conditional probabilities, lateral propagation toward the “ UM ” node also occurs, showing a very slight change. Following this, forward propagation continues toward the fused node $MD-MP-SUad$, and the nodes CC and FC . Significant changes occur in the values of MP and MD (material problem and defect). The probabilities of CC and FC increase. From the $MD-MP-SUad$ node, forward propagation continues to the fused node $CR-ANC$, where the probability of ANC increases. Lateral propagation occurs toward the MM node, which shows a slight decrease in its probability due to evidence indicating a root cause of customer refusal related

Figure 10: Results of Evidence Propagation in the Bayesian network when $MTI=1$ and $CR=1$

to an inadequate mold temperature. From this MM node, backward propagation occurs to the PM node. Since the change in the probability of MM is slight, the change in PM is also slight.

3.6 Case IV: Customer Refusal, $CR=1$; Mould Temperature Inadequate, $MTI=1$ and Problem Mould, $PM=1$

Now, let us consider the case where $MTI = 1$, $CR = 1$, and $PM = 1$. In this case as shown in Figure 11. We start from the results of the run where $MTI = 1$ and $CR = 1$, and then add the new evidence $PM = 1$. In all cases where backward and lateral propagation occurred, the probability coefficients of the Bayesian network must be updated. From the PM node, forward propagation occurs to the MM node. From this node, forward propagation continues to the “CR-ANC” node, along with lateral propagation toward the “MD-MP-SUad” node. From there, backward propagation proceeds to the “B-F-VIH-SU” node. From this node, forward propagation occurs toward the CC and FC nodes, as well as backward propagation to the “MTI-FM” and UM nodes. Although evidence of PM (misplacement of material) is present as a cause of customer refusal, this only slightly decreases the probabilities of the other nodes, because evidence of MTI (inadequate mold temperature) is also present.

This developed method allows tracking the flow of evidence propagation and generating an explanation of the results.

3.7 Comparison between methods

We compared the results of the message-passing propagation method and the newly proposed method for all situations, finding that the results are identical, as

Figure 11: Results of Evidence Propagation in the Bayesian network when $MTI=1$, $CR=1$ and $PM=1$

is shown in Table 2. The variables are listed in the first column and are referred to by their acronyms, whose meanings are defined in Table I. The meanings of the acronyms in the first row are as follows: MP (Marginal Probability), MIT (in this case, the evidence Mould Inadequate Temperature was observed to be true), CR (in this case, the evidence Customer Refusal was observed to be true), MIT CR (in this case, the evidences Mould Inadequate Temperature and Customer Refusal were observed to be true), and MIT CR PM (in this case, the evidences Mould Inadequate Temperature, Customer Refusal, and Placing Material were observed to be true). The results were obtained from the Bayesian network using both the standard evidence propagation method and the new method developed in this work. Since both methods are exact, they yield identical results, which can be verified in the code provided in the supplementary material.

3.8 Application B: pressurized fluid storage tank

An example taken from the book *Expert Systems and Probabilistic Networks* by E. Castillo et al. [Castillo, 1998] is presented. It addresses a pressurized fluid storage tank, where the fluid is introduced with the aid of a pressure vessel. The operation of the equipment and the control system is described in greater detail in the referenced book. Figure 12 shows the Bayesian network used in this example. The nodes and arcs represent the conditional probability relationships among the variables. This Bayesian network is used to determine the failure probabilities of the equipment. The Table 3 presents the values used for the Bayesian network in this case.

Table 2: Bayesian network results using standard and proposed exact propagation methods (identical; see supplementary code)

Variable	MP	MIT	CR	MTI-CR	MTI-CR-PM
FM	0.4000	0.4000	0.4091	0.4074	0.4051
PM	0.7000	0.7000	0.7684	0.7462	1.0000
MTI	0.6000	1.0000	0.6594	1.0000	1.0000
UM	0.2500	0.2500	0.2745	0.2758	0.2657
F	0.4120	0.5800	0.4539	0.5967	0.5915
B	0.5400	0.9000	0.5976	0.9062	0.9043
VIH	0.3160	0.4200	0.3338	0.4219	0.4213
SU	0.3194	0.4824	0.3917	0.5400	0.5173
MM	0.6160	0.6160	0.7127	0.6813	0.8873
MP	0.2962	0.4388	0.3227	0.4444	0.4427
MD	0.5899	0.7077	0.6969	0.7713	0.7515
FC	0.3502	0.4930	0.3858	0.5072	0.5028
ANC	0.5783	0.6468	0.6221	0.6756	0.7163
CR	0.7566	0.8315	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
CC	0.3002	0.3990	0.3171	0.4008	0.4003

Table 3: Variables used in the bayesian network of the figure 12

Variable	Name	Father Nodes	Probability
<i>A</i>	Pressure switch		0.998,0.002
<i>B</i>	Tank		0.999,0.001
<i>C</i>	Relay		0.997,0.003
<i>D</i>	Relay		0.99,0.010
<i>E</i>	Interrupter		0.999,0.001
<i>F</i>	Time Relay		0.99,0.010
<i>G</i>		D,F	1.0,0.0,0.0,1.0,0.0,1.0,0.0,1.0
<i>H</i>		E,G	1.0,0.0,0.0,1.0,0.0,1.0,0.0,1.0
<i>I</i>		A,H	1.0,0.0,1.0,0.0,1.0,0.0,0.0,1.0
<i>J</i>		C,I	1.0,0.0,0.0,1.0,0.0,1.0,0.0,1.0
<i>K</i>		B,J	1.0,0.0,0.0,1.0,0.0,1.0,0.0,1.0

The standard message-passing method and the proposed method were both executed—not with the aim of proving the correctness of the proposed method, but rather to verify that its Python implementation was carried out correctly and to identify potential bugs. The table 4 shows the agreement between the two methods in computing the probabilities, where it can be observed that both yield the same results.

Figure 12: Bayesian Network used in this example

Table 4: Comparison between results obtained from traditional and the new method

Variable	DF-BN	DFJ-BN	DF-NM	DFJ-NM
A	0.0020	0.4005	0.0020	0.4005
B	0.0010	0.0010	0.0010	0.0010
C	0.0030	0.6007	0.0030	0.6007
D	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
E	0.0010	0.0010	0.0010	0.0010
F	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
G	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
H	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
I	0.0020	0.4005	0.0020	0.4005
J	0.0050	1.0000	0.0050	1.0000
K	0.0060	1.0000	0.0060	1.0000

3.9 Evaluation of Probabilistic Queries in Bayesian Networks

It is possible to compute additional quantities using this new method and the use of probability factors. If one wishes to compute the joint probability of nodes D and E, the following procedure should be applied. According to the route indicated by the bayesian network shown in the figure 12, we calculate the probability of $G = G_k$ and D_i as is shown in the equation:

$$(d_i g_k) = \sum_j \Phi(G_k | D_i, F_j) d_i f_j \quad (38)$$

And then, the process would proceed as follows, we calculate the probability of $E = E_l$ and D_i as is shown in the equation::

$$(d_i e_l) = \sum_{m,k} \Phi(H_m | G_k, E_l)(d_i g_k) e_l \quad (39)$$

It is important to clarify that, in cases where the probability factor is equal to the conditional probability, the joint probability of D and E results as the product of the probabilities of D and E, as expected under the assumption of independence between D and E, which is consistent with the structure of the Bayesian network. However, this is not the case in all situations. If, for any reason, a backward propagation flow reaches node H and G, the probability factors are no longer equal to the conditional probabilities. In such cases, the joint probability must be computed using the previously described formula. This procedure allows the computation of joint probabilities taking into account the structure and dependencies defined in the network.

3.10 Calculation of the most probable explanation MPE

Another way in which this method can be used is for the computation of the Most Probable Explanation (MPE), which involves finding the top-k most probable explanations given the observed evidence. Let us consider the previous case where the evidence is $D = 1$, $F = 1$, and $J = 1$. We calculate the Most Probable Explanation (MPE) starting from node J. Although it is also possible to compute it from the initial nodes, we believe it is more appropriate to begin with node J because it allows us to better capture the influence of the nearest nodes. These nearby nodes have a stronger effect on the explanation and are therefore more suitable for generating it due to their proximity to the evidence, as indicated in the Table 5.

This calculation method ultimately yields the three most probable paths: two with high probability values and one with a very low value. Since all variables are involved, the first observation is that paths 2 and 3 can be merged into a single explanation, as variable C is not crucial in this context. Path 1, however, does require variable C in the explanation. Consequently, we are left with two possible explanations. Examining these two explanations closely, the difference lies solely in variables A and C, which allows us to generate the failure diagnosis as follows: In both explanations, the evidence shows $D = 1$ and $F = 1$, corresponding to failures in relay D and timer relay F. The difference is that path 2 proposes a failure in relay A, while path 1 suggests a failure in relay C. Although a joint failure involving both parts could be considered, its probability is very low.

3.11 Parallelization of the Inference Algorithm

The algorithm can be parallelized, for example, by using the previous case and assigning probability values as indicated in the Table 6. The Bayesian network is executed using all the available evidence. The resulting values are presented in the first column, labeled DFJ.

This network can be divided into two parts: one comprising nodes F, D, and G, and the other consisting of the remaining nodes. For example, we can

Table 5: Table of explanations generated from the node J

Stage	Route	Probability
1	I=0,C=1	0.5995
	I=1,C=0	0.3993
	I=1,C=1	0.0012
2	C=1	0.6007
	H=1,A=1,I=1,C=0	0.3993
3	C=1	0.6007
	G=1,E=0,H=1,A=1,I=1,C=0	0.3989
	G=1,E=1,H=1,A=1,I=1,C=0	0.0004
4	C=1	0.6007
	D=1,F=1,G=1,H=1,A=1,I=1,C=0	0.3993

Table 6: Variables used in the Bayesian network of Figure 12, with corresponding conditional probabilities (distinct from those in Table 3)

Variable	Name	Father Nodes	Probability
A	Pressure switch		0.998,0.002
B	Tank		0.999,0.001
C	Relay		0.997,0.003
D	Relay		0.99,0.010
E	Interrupter		0.999,0.001
F	Time Relay		0.99,0.010
G		D,F	0.6,0.4,0.3,0.7,0.2,0.8,0.1,0.9
H		E,G	0.8,0.2,0.2,0.8,0.2,0.8,0.2,0.8
I		A,H	0.8,0.2,0.8,0.2,0.8,0.2,0.2,0.8
J		C,I	0.8,0.2,0.2,0.8,0.2,0.8,0.2,0.8
K		B,J	0.8,0.2,0.2,0.8,0.2,0.8,0.2,0.8

run the algorithm solely on the first subnet (with evidence $D=1,F=1$) without propagating this evidence to the second subnet, obtaining the results shown in the DF-R1 column of the table 7. Then, we run the evidence $J=1$ on the second Bayesian network, obtaining the results indicated in the third column J-R2R1. The same evidence is also passed to the first part of the network. Finally, the evidence ($D=1,F=1$) is allowed to run in the second network, producing the results listed in the last column DF-R2. These results match those in the first and fourth columns, confirming the anticipated capability of the algorithm to operate in parallel. It is important to note, however, that there is a limitation for parallelization: the connection point between the two subnetworks must be unique.

Table 7: Variables used in the bayesian network

Variable	DFJ	DF-R1	J-R2R1	DF-R1
A	0.0036	0.0020	0.0035	0.0035
B	0.0010	0.0010	0.0010	0.0010
C	0.0075	0.0030	0.0075	0.0075
D	1.0000	1.0000	1.0001	1.0000
E	0.0010	0.0010	0.0010	0.0010
F	1.0000	1.0000	1.0001	1.0000
G	0.9001	0.8010	0.8012	0.9002
H	0.7405	0.6807	0.6812	0.7406
I	0.4991	0.2008	0.4990	0.4992
J	1.0000	0.3219	1.0000	1.0000
K	0.8000	0.3936	0.8000	0.8001

4 Conclusions

This article presents the development of a new algorithm for evidence propagation in Bayesian networks. Unlike previous algorithms, which are based on message propagation between the nodes of the Bayesian network, this algorithm allows evidence to be propagated from one node to another, enabling the tracking of the evidence flow in Bayesian networks.

It would have the following advantages:

- Traceability of the evidence. The algorithm proposed in this paper allows one to calculate in an exact way the probability of the nodes without losing the evidence propagation path. This ability is important in the case of expert systems, not only to trace their performance during the construction and evaluation of the system, but also to justify their results when the system is operating.
- Real-time updating. In this approach, probabilities would be updated immediately after incorporating each piece of evidence, which is ideal in systems that need to make real-time decisions useful in dynamic systems, such as medical diagnostics, recommender systems or real-time monitoring, where information may arrive sequentially.
- Overtime Reduction. In this approach, the calculation is incremental, avoiding the need to process the entire network at each step. This is useful in real-time monitoring problems, such as anomaly detection in sensor networks, where data arrives continuously and may change frequently.
- Modularity and scalability. By not requiring global processing of the entire network for each computation, the method can scale better in large, modular networks, where some parts of the network can be processed independently. The network allows incorporating new evidence in specific parts without affecting the rest, which avoids unnecessary computations and improves efficiency in dynamic systems.

- Splitting computations. Dividing into parallel processes reduces the time required for evidence propagation, especially in large or densely connected networks. Allowing faster inference in time-sensitive applications, which can be useful in artificial intelligence applications in autonomous vehicles, robotics or early warning systems.
- Prioritization of evidence. By processing evidence one by one, it can be incorporated strategically, prioritizing the most relevant or critical evidence first. This is not as straightforward in traditional methods, where all evidence is propagated simultaneously. It is useful in contexts such as critical decision making, where certain evidence may have a greater impact on the final outcome.

The method is capable of finding the Most Probable Explanation (MPE), which provides the most likely causes of failure in a system represented by a Bayesian network in applications of artificial intelligence.

5 Future Work

We are aware that there is still much to explore in this line of research. Among the aspects that could be further investigated, one possibility is to adapt the method so that probabilities are updated immediately after each new piece of evidence is incorporated. This would be particularly useful for real-time decision-making systems operating in dynamic environments, such as real-time monitoring applications where evidence arrives sequentially.

Another promising direction is to enable the method to trace the flow of evidence propagation through the network, allowing the generation of interpretable explanations that help users understand how the system arrived at its conclusions. Although the current algorithm is implemented in a sequential manner, it is possible to adapt it to handle multiple pieces of evidence simultaneously without losing the logical sequence of probabilistic reasoning. A potential direction for future work is to explore the subdivision of the Bayesian network into modular components that can compute their local probability distributions independently. These modules would then be able to communicate with each other to adjust the probabilities of their nodes based on the information received from other modules.

6 supplement

The code used in this article can be found in the GitHub repository <https://github.com/eduardomaciasavila70-again/new-bayesian-network-code>

References

[Brahim, 2019] Ben Brahim, S.A. Addouche, A. El Mhamedi, Y. Boujelbene: “Build a Bayesian Network from FMECA in the production of Automotive Parts: Diagnosis and Prediction”; FAC PapersOnLine, 2019, 2572–2577.

- [Belu, 2013] Belu, N., Khassawneh, N., and Al Ali, A.R.: “Implementation of failure mode, effects and criticality analysis in the production of automotive parts”; *Calitatea* vol. 14, 2013
- [Blei, 2017] D. Blei, A. Kucukelbir, J.D. McAuliffe: “Variational Inference: A Review for Statisticians”; *Journal of the American Statistical Association* vol. 112, No. 512, 2017, 859-877.
- [Castillo, 1998] Enrique Castillo, Jose Manuel Gutierrez, Ali S. Hadi: “Sistemas Expertos y Modelos de Redes Probabilísticas”; (1998).
- [Fung, 1990] Fung, R., Chang, K.: “ConTexts: Adaptable hypermedia”; *Proc. Adapt. Hypermedia and Adapt. Web-Based Sys. Int. Conf., Lect. Notes in Comp. Sci.* 1892, Springer, Berlin (Aug 2000), 369-375.
- [Kim, 1990] Kim, J. H., Pearl, J.: “Weighing and Integrating Evidence for Stochastic Simulation in Bayesian Networks”; *Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence*, North Holland, Amsterdam, 1990, 209–219.
- [Koller, 2009] D. Koller and N. Friedman: “Probabilistic Graphical Models, Principles and Techniques”; The MIT Press, 2009.
- [Lacave, 2002] C. Lacave, F. J. Díez: “A review of explanation methods for Bayesian networks”. *The Knowledge Engineering Review* vol. 17, 2002, 107–127.
- [Pearl, 1988] Pearl: “Probabilistic Reasoning in Intelligent Systems: Networks of Plausible Inference”; Morgan Kaufmann, San Mateo, CA, 1988
- [Pearl, 1986] Pearl, J.: “A Constraint-Propagation Approach to Probabilistic Reasoning”; *Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence*, North Holland, Amsterdam, 1986, 357–369
- [Pearl, 1987] Pearl, J.: “Evidential Reasoning Using Stochastic Simulation of Causal Models”; *Artificial Intelligence*, 1987, 245–257.
- [Renooij, 1999] S. Renooij, L. van der Gaag: “Enhancing QPN for trade-off resolution”; *Proceedings of the 15th Conference on Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence*, Stockholm, Sweden, 1999, 559-566.
- [Shachter, 1990] Shachter, R. and Peot, M.: “Simulation Approaches to General Probabilistic Inference on Belief Networks”; *Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence*, North Holland, Amsterdam, 1990.
- [Suermondt, 1990] Suermondt, H. J. and Cooper, G. F.: “Probabilistic Inference in Multiply Connected Belief Networks Using Loop Cutsets”; *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning*, 1990, 283–306.
- [Tomasetti, 2022] N. Tomasetti, C. Forbes, A. Panagiotelis: “Updating Variational Bayes: Fast sequential posterior inference”; *IStatistics and Computing*, vol. 32, 2022.
- [Wermann, 1990] M. Wermann: “Fundamental concepts of qualitative probabilistic networks. *Artificial Intelligence*” *Artificial Intelligence* vol. 44 no.1, 1990, 257-303
- [Winn, 2005] J. Winn, C.M. Bishop: “Variational Message Passing” *A Journal of Machine Learning Research* vol. 6, 2005, 661–694